

Electrostatic Effects in Some Lanthanide-EDTA-Alizarine Red Sulphonic Acid Ternary Complexes

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A pH-metric study of 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 mixed-ligand complexes of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} has been carried out in aqueous medium using EDTA as primary ligand and alizarine red sulphonic acid (ARS) as secondary ligand (H₂L) employing Irving-Rossotti titration technique, at 25° and ionic strength of 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄. The effect of electrostatic repulsion between [LN-EDTA]⁻ and L³⁺ species on the stability of the ternary complexes has been studied.

The general order of stability for the binary and ternary complexes is found to be $\log K_{MA}^M > \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, whereas the trend in $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values with respect to metal ions is La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}. Validity of Born relation has been studied. The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values have been correlated with certain fundamental properties of lanthanides (LN), viz. standard entropies (S_M^o), standard oxidation potentials (E^o), sum of the first three ionisation potentials (ΣI) and total angular momentum (L). Mathematical expression for the log-log correlations of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, vs $\log K_{MA}^M$ has also been derived and discussed.

ALTHOUGH extensive work has been carried out spectrophotometrically on alizarine red sulphonic acid complexes but very few have been studied potentiometrically¹⁻⁴. The present communication deals with the pH-metric studies of 1:1 binary and 1:1:1 mixed complexes of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} using EDTA as primary ligand and alizarine red sulphonic acid (monosodium salt monohydrate ARS) as secondary ligand, employing Irving-Rossotti titration technique at 25° and ionic strength of 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄.

Experimental

Standard solutions of lanthanide metal ions (LN³⁺) were prepared by dissolving their nitrates of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Sm^{III} in doubly distilled water. The oxides of Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} were dissolved in minimum quantity of perchloric acid, excess of which was successively evaporated. Disodium salt of EDTA was used. The two remaining protons were also taken into consideration. Usual titration sets for the study of 1:1 binary (ML or MA) and 1:1:1 mixed complexes (MAL) were prepared. Use of dilute solutions (10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) was made to avoid the possibility of formation of polynuclear species. The sets were titrated against 0.2 mol dm⁻³ carbonate free NaOH and the pH was recorded on an Elico model LI-120 digital type pH-meter.

Results and Discussion

The values of metal-ligand stability constants of 1:1 binary ($\log K_{ML}^M$) and 1:1:1 ternary complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) as computed by Irving-Rossotti⁵ pH-titration technique along with their $\Delta \log K$ ($\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$), ΔG ($\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) and $\log \beta_{MAL}^M$ ($\log \beta_{MAL}^M = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} + \log K_{MA}^M$, i.e. overall stability constant of the ternary complexes MAL) have been recorded in Table 1.

The ligand curve (not shown) indicates the liberation of two protons, one at pH 4.00 and the other at 10.50. The practical proton-ligand stability constants $\log K_n^H$ were calculated for \bar{n}_H (formation function corresponding to proton-ligand formation constant) values lying in the range $0 < \bar{n}_H < 2$. The formation of mixed ligand complex, MAL takes place according to the equilibria $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$. Theoretical composite curve⁶ was also drawn. The non-superimposable nature of the composite curve on the experimental mixed-complex curve indicates the formation of mixed-complex. The formation of mixed-complex takes place at the pH where the formation of hydroxo-species can be ignored. The plot of $\bar{n}/[L]$ vs $[L]$ (where \bar{n} = formation function of the complex ML or MAL, and $[L]$ = free ligand exponent) is found to be smooth indicating the absence of polynuclear species.

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1:1 BINARY ($\log K_{ML}^M$) AND 1:1:1 TERNARY ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) COMPLEXES, ΔG , $\Delta \log K$, $\log \beta_{MAL}^M$ VALUES FOR THE TERNARY LANTHANIDE-EDTA-ARS SYSTEMS*

I = 0.2 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ Temp. = 25°

	Metal ions				
	La ³⁺	Ce ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺
$\log K_{ML}^M$	9.98	10.06	10.09	10.13	10.21
	(±0.04)	(±0.02)	(±0.03)	(±0.04)	(±0.01)
$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	7.81	7.97	8.12	8.21	8.36
	(±0.04)	(±0.02)	(±0.03)	(±0.04)	(±0.05)
$-\Delta \log K$	2.19	2.09	1.87	1.82	1.85
$-\Delta G(\text{Kcal/mole})$	10.72	10.94	11.15	11.26	11.47
$\log \beta_{MAL}^M$	19.44	19.80	20.37	20.74	21.20

* The values of standard deviations for $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ are given in parentheses.

A perusal of the values of stability constants (Table 1) shows that the general trend of stability for the binary and ternary complexes is $\log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ are obviously lower due to coulombic repulsion between the negatively charged primary complex [LN-EDTA]⁻ and the incoming secondary ligand L²⁺. The $\Delta \log K$ values are, therefore, negative. Steric and statistical factors⁷ are also expected to contribute towards lowering of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values as compared to $\log K_{ML}^M$.

The order of stability with respect to metal ions for binary as well as ternary complexes has been found to be La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}, which is the order of their decreasing ionic radii.

In lanthanides the 4fⁿ electrons are well shielded from ligand perturbations by the outer 5s and 5p orbitals. The metal-ligand bond should, therefore, be ionic with minimal covalent contribution. Born relation⁸, $E = Z^2/r [(1-1/D)]$ (where E = energy of complexation, Z = charge on metal ion, r = crystal radius of metal ion, D = dielectric constant of medium) has been tested for the present series of ternary complexes. Plots of $\log K_{ML}^M$ or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs Z^2/r (Fig. 1) are slightly curved, which may be due to partial covalent nature⁹ of the bond and varying degrees of stabilisation caused due to ligand field. Similar observations have been noted¹⁰⁻¹³ for other lanthanide complexes.

The $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values have been correlated with some fundamental properties of lanthanides, viz. standard entropies (S_M^0), standard oxidation potentials (E^0), sum of the first three ionisation potentials (ΣI) and total angular momentum (L).

A linear variation of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ and $\log K_{ML}^M$ with S_M^0 (Fig. 1) indicates that the free energy changes during complexation are essentially entropy changes.

Fig. 1. $\log K_{ML}^M$ (○) and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (▼) vs Z^2/r and S_M^0 values of lanthanide metal ions.

A similar trend has been observed for 1:1 LN-EDTA complexes¹⁴. The standard electrode potentials (E^0) of the lanthanides used when plotted against the stability constants yield a linear plot (Fig. 2). The free energy change corresponding to the standard electrode potentials comprises mainly the heat of formation of the bare lanthanide metal ion and its heat of hydration, the latter being the heat of ligation of water molecules, one may expect a gradual increase in $\log K$ values with decrease in E^0 values for lanthanides.

Fig. 2. $\log K_{ML}^M$ (○) and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (▼) vs E^0 and ΣI of lanthanide metal ions.

The ionisation potentials may be regarded as a measure of electron affinity and a direct correlation

between the stability constants ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ or $\log K_{ML}^M$) and the overall ionisation potential ($\leq I$) of the lanthanides may be possible. Fig. 2 shows that the plots of $\log K$ vs $\leq I$ are linear. La^{III} falls below the line in each case as its $\leq I$ value lies relatively closer to that of Ce^{III} .

Recently, attempt has been made¹⁵ to explain the so-called 'Gd-break' (also double-double effect^{16,17} or tetrad effect^{18,19}) by correlating the stability constants of complexes and several other properties of the lanthanides with the numerical values of their total angular momentum (L). These plots were four segmented inclined 'W' (i.e., \approx) type for the entire series from La^{III} to Lu^{III} . Fig. 3 shows the inclined 'W' plots of $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs L. Only the first segment is possible in the present case. The plots are almost linear. The validity of the results has been further tested by drawing log-log plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{MA}^M$. Mathematical expression derived for this correlation²⁰ is,

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = \log K_{MA}^M + (2.303RT)^{-1} [G_L^0 - G_A^0] + (2G_{MA}^0 - G_{MAL}^0 - G_M^0).$$

Fig. 3. $\log K_{ML}^M$ (O) or $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ (v) vs L values of lanthanide metal ions (L=total angular momentum of lanthanide metal ions).

From the expression $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ is expected to vary linearly with $\log K_{MA}^M$ provided the first term within brackets on the right hand side is constant and the second term is either negligible in comparison to the first term or constant or a linear function of $\log K_{MA}^M$. The first two conditions will lead to a plot of unit slope and the third to a non-unit slope. The best straight line plot drawn by using the method of least squares gives the equation,

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = 0.39 \log K_{MA}^M - 0.86.$$

Yatsimirskii and Kostromina²¹ have calculated extrastabilisation energy (i.e., l.f.s.e.) for the 1:1 binary LN-EDTA chelates considering them to be octahedral. Although such a procedure would lead to somewhat approximate values, but it gives an idea of the order of magnitude of l.f.s.e. in solution. The values of l.f.s.e. and 14 Dq in the present series have been calculated using the same procedure. The maximum value of 14 Dq corresponds to 140 cm^{-1} which is less than the values obtained from spectroscopic measurements²². It has been shown²³ that the electron pairing energy in $4f$ sub-level in lanthanides is about 8000 cm^{-1} , which is much higher than the maximum value of l.f.s.e. in the present case. This will thus favour only a 'high-spin' distribution of electrons in LN-EDTA chelates.

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